

Condensation of Pyruvic Acid with Aldehydes.

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Claisen and Claparede (*Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2472) first condensed pyruvic acid with benzaldehyde using dry hydrochloric acid gas as condensing agent and subsequently Erlenmeyer (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2567; 1904, 37, 1318) and Lubruzyuska and Smedley (*Biochem. J.*, 1913, 7, 375) studied the condensation of pyruvic acid with different aldehydes, *e.g.*, benzaldehyde, cinnamic aldehyde, anisaldehyde and piperonal in presence of dilute caustic potash solution. The reaction proceeded in all cases at the laboratory temperature and the time required varied from 2 to 7 days and the yields varied from 50 to 70% of the theoretical.

The object of the present work is to study further the condensation of pyruvic acid with benzaldehyde, substituted benzaldehydes and a few other aldehydes, aliphatic and heterocyclic, with a view to work out the optimum conditions under which the reaction may take place and also to see if the resulting α -keto- β -unsaturated acids can be converted into ring compounds on treatment with suitable dehydrating agents.

It has been found that a saturated solution of alcoholic caustic potash is the best condensing agent, which effects the condensation of benzaldehyde with pyruvic acid completely in 15—20 minutes at the ordinary temperature producing the potassium salt of the acid in good yield. The acid is identical in properties to the compound described by Claisen and Claparede (*loc. cit.*) and also by Erlenmeyer (*loc. cit.*). It gives a hydrazone and the presence of the ethylene linking is proved by the formation of a dibromo derivative. On heating the acid with acetic acid and fused sodium acetate at 180-90° ring formation takes place and the resulting product, decomposing at 115-20° and producing phthalic acid on oxidation, has been definitely identified with β -naphthaquinone.

The condensations of the nitrobenzaldehydes with pyruvic acid in presence of alcoholic potash have led to interesting results. The unsaturated acid from *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde is yellow.

A remarkable phenomenon has been noticed on heating the yellow acid to 160-65°, when it changes to a red variety, which has been found to have the same composition as the yellow variety, the two varieties differing also in their solubilities. The red variety is again transformed into the yellow variety on continued boiling with dilute alcohol. This may be a case of geometrical isomerism or chromo-isomerism (nitro and acinitro compounds).

It has been further observed that the yellow compound, when heated to 175-80°, at first changes to the red variety and is then transformed into a ring compound which is insoluble in sodium bicarbonate and does not melt up to 230°. As the possibility of the ring formation is greater when the COOH group and the phenyl radical are on the same side, it appears that the red form corresponds to the *syn*-structure and the yellow form to the *anti*-structure. It has not been possible to isolate two isomers in the case of the acid derived from *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, which is dull red. In this case ready ring formation does not take place. The condensation of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde with pyruvic acid leads to the formation of 10% indigo and a small quantity of a dull red compound which has not been further investigated. Indigo is probably thus formed :

Cinnamic aldehyde, piperonal and anisaldehyde have been condensed with pyruvic acid and it has been generally found that the condensations readily take place with alcoholic caustic potash, while it requires several days for the completion of the reaction in the presence of hydrochloric acid.

As previously noticed by Erlenmeyer (*loc. cit.*) and also by Labrazyuska and Smedley (*loc. cit.*) the unsaturated acids derived from cinnamic aldehyde, as well as piperonal, also exist in two isomeric forms, one variety readily changing to the other form. All these keto acids are converted into ring compounds by heating with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate; the acid from cinnamic aldehyde producing an eight-membered ring compound (*cf.* Sen and Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 402) which is insoluble in sodium

carbonate but breaks on heating with dilute alkalis and also with water.

Furfural and citral have also easily been condensed with pyruvic acid in the presence of alcoholic caustic potash to produce the keto acids which yield hydrazones and bromo derivatives; but it has not been possible to obtain ring compounds from them.

The condensation of the hydroxybenzaldehydes, *e. g.*, *o*- and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehydes, β -resorcyaldehyde with pyruvic acid is an interesting study; while *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde condenses in the presence of alcoholic potash as well as hydrochloric acid gas to form the keto-unsaturated acid, salicylaldehyde produces using either of the condensing agents a mixture of two compounds; one, a yellow crystalline substance decomposing at 185-90° and another, a red compound. It appears that the yellow product is the free hydroxy acid, while the red compound is the lactone, which is insoluble in

sodium carbonate but breaks and dissolves when kept in contact with water or with dilute caustic alkalis. The free acid, on boiling with strong hydrochloric acid, produces the lactone (red compound).

β -Resorcyaldehyde condenses with pyruvic acid at 220° using concentrated hydrochloric acid to produce a seven-membered lactone, which breaks up in contact with dilute alkalis. It is interesting to note that these seven-membered lactones from salicylaldehyde and β -resorcyaldehyde have dyeing properties like similar compounds from levulinic acid (*cf.* Sen and Roy, *loc. cit.*); the lactone from salicylaldehyde dyeing silk a yellowish-red shade while the lactone from

β -resorcylaldehyde dyes a deeper shade. Coumarin, a six-membered lactone, possesses neither colour nor any dyeing property. The dyeing property and colour of these lactones can only be attributed to their being seven-membered ones, with two CO groups.

Glucose has also been condensed with pyruvic acid in the presence of dry hydrochloric acid gas to form in 90% yield a deep red compound, which behaves like a lactone breaking up when kept in contact with dilute alkalis. This compound has probably got the following structure :

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cinnamylformic acid.—To a mixture of pyruvic acid (3.5 c. c.) and benzaldehyde (5.5 c. c.), alcoholic caustic potash (2.5 g. in 10 c. c. rectified spirit) was added drop by drop in the cold and the mixture shaken. The colour deepened and in 15 minutes the mixture solidified. The solid mass of potassium salt was purified from hot alcohol. (Found: K, 18.12. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{K}$ requires K, 18.22 per cent). The free acid is a yellow thick liquid and was purified by washing with hot water and was then extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried and the ether evaporated off in vacuum, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 67.67; H, 4.51. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$ requires C, 68.19 ; H, 4.55 per cent).

The *dibromo derivative*, prepared by shaking the alcoholic solution of the acid with bromine water, crystallised from dilute alcohol as yellowish needles. (Found: Br, 47.71. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{Br}_2$ requires Br, 47.61 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual manner, was obtained from dilute alcohol as an orange-red compound. (Found: N, 10.2. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 10.53 per cent).

The ring compound (β -naphthaquinone) was obtained by heating the acid with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate at $180\text{--}90^\circ$ for nearly 3 hours. The whole mass was then poured into a solution of sodium bicarbonate and left overnight. A red mass separated which was repeatedly washed with hot water and finally purified from rectified spirit. It decomposes at $115\text{--}20^\circ$ and is identical with β -naphthaquinone in solubilities and in other properties.

The other compounds, prepared in a similar way, are described in the Table.

TABLE.

Aldehyde used and the derivatives of the product.	Formula.	Analysis		Remarks.
		Found.	Calc.	
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	$C_{10}H_7O_5N$	N, 6.07%	6.33%	Yellow crystals, readily soluble in acetic acid. alcohol, acetone; changes to red at 165°. Red variety transformed to yellow by boiling with alcohol and water.
— K salt.	$C_{10}H_6O_6NK$	K, 15.17	15.06.	Red.
— dibromo derivative	$C_{10}H_7O_6NBr_2$	Br, 41.58	42.00	Needles from alcohol, soften at 95°.
— phenylhydrazone	$C_{16}H_{13}O_4N_3$	N, 13.49	13.55	Needles from alcohol, m. p. 186°.
Ring compound	$C_{10}H_5O_4N$	N, 7.09	6.90	Prepared from the yellow acid by heating to 170-180°. Small needles from alcohol or acetone not melting up to 230°; also obtained by heating the acid with acetic anhydride.
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde.	$C_{10}H_7O_5N$	N, 6.21	6.38	Red, does not melt up to 260°. K salt very hygroscopic.
— dibromo derivative	$C_{10}H_7O_6NBr_2$	Br, 41.8	42.00	Yellow from dilute alcohol.
— phenylhydrazone	$C_{16}H_{13}O_4N_3$	N, 13.65	13.55	Red.
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	$C_{16}H_{10}O_2N_2$	N, 10.74	10.69	Indigo.
Cinnamic aldehyde	$C_{12}H_{10}O_3$	C, 70.92	71.29	Orange-red, m. p. 74°, soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and acetone. If kept in a vacuum desiccator for some days the orange-red variety changes to yellow, m. p. 104-5°.
		H, 4.51	4.95	

Aldehyde used and derivatives of the product.	Formula.	Analysis		Remarks.
		Found.	Calc.	
— K-salt	$C_{12}H_9O_3K$	K, 16.16%	16.25%	Yellow.
— phenylhydrazone	$C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_2$	N, 9.72	9.61	Red, m. p. 152°.
— dibromo derivative	$C_{12}H_{10}O_3Br_2$	Br, 44.68	44.22	Colourless, m. p. 114°.
— ring compound	$C_{12}H_8O_3$	C, 78.48	78.2	Prepared by heating with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate at 200-10°. Red, m. p. 223° soluble in alcohol, acetone, acetic acid, unstable and dissolves in dilute alkali.
		H, 4.82	4.82	
Piperonal	$C_{11}H_8O_5$	C, 59.56	60.01	Yellow, changes colour at 70° and then melts at 162-63°. The yellow variety changes to a beautiful orange-red variety (m. p. 162-63°) in contact with HCl or heated to 70°.
— K-salt	$C_{11}H_7O_6K$	H, 3.95	3.63	
— dibromo derivative	$C_{11}H_8O_6Br_2$	K, 14.96	15.12	M. p. 102°.
— phenylhydrazone	$C_{17}H_{14}O_4N_2$	Br, 42.42	42.10	Yellow, m. p. 174°.
— ring compound	$C_{11}H_6O_4$	N, 9.34;	9.03	Prepared by heating with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate at 200-10°, m. p. 160°.
		C, 64.92	65.34	
		H, 3.22	2.97	
Anisaldehyde	$C_{11}H_{10}O_4$	C, 63.95	64.67	Yellow, soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, ether, chloroform, acetone and hot water.
— K-salt	$C_{11}H_9O_4K$	H, 5.32	4.85	
— dibromo derivative	$C_{11}H_{10}O_4Br_2$	K, 15.74	15.99	Colourless, m. p. 82-85°.
— phenylhydrazone	$C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2$	Br, 44.17	43.71	Orange-red, m. p. 158°.
— ring compound	$C_{11}H_8O_3$	N, 9.49	9.46	Prepared by heating with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate at 200°. Red, sparingly soluble in alcohol.
		C, 70.08	70.21	
		H, 4.61	4.26	

Aldehyde used and the derivatives of the product.	Formula.	Analysis.		Remarks.
		Found.	Calc.	
Furfuraldehyde	$C_8H_6O_4$	C, 57.45%	57.84%	Yellow, m. p. 110°.
—		H, 4.20	3.62	
— K-salt	$C_8H_5O_4K$	K, 19.36	19.12	Yellow.
— phenylhydrazone	$C_{14}H_{12}O_3N_2$	N, 10.93	10.94	Deep yellow, m. p. 162° (decomp.).
Citral	$C_{13}H_{18}O_3$	C, 70.06	70.26	Reddish liquid of thick consistency, soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, acetone and ether.
		H, 4.52	8.11	
— K-salt	$C_{13}H_{17}O_3K$	K, 15.36	15.00	The salt separates as a pasty mass which solidifies at 120°.
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	$C_{10}H_8O_4$	C, 62.17	62.5	Dry HCl is used as the condensing agent. Red liquid.
		H, 4.56	4.17	

Condensation of salicylaldehyde with pyruvic acid. (i) *With alcoholic potash.*—Pyruvic acid (3.5 c. c.) and salicylaldehyde (5 c. c.) were condensed in presence of caustic potash (2.5 g.) dissolved in alcohol (10 c. c.). On acidification two products were obtained: one is a yellow crystalline substance found to be the free acid while the other, a red compound, is the lactone of the acid.

(ii) *With HCl.*—The condensation was also effected by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas through a mixture of the two and leaving the whole thing for a week. On pouring the mixture into a little alcohol, the yellow free acid separated. It was purified by dissolving in caustic soda, the alkaline solution extracted with ether to remove unaltered aldehyde and then acidified. It was finally purified from alcohol or chloroform, yield 20%. It decomposes at 185-90°. (Found: C, 62.33; H, 4.61. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ requires C, 62.5; H, 4.17 per cent).

On diluting the alcoholic solution after removal of the yellow free acid, a red compound was obtained. It was purified by washing with chloroform to remove the free acid. It does not melt up to 235°. It is soluble in alcohol, ether, acetic acid, insoluble in benzene, carbon bisulphide and carbon tetrachloride. It is very unstable easily changing to yellow acid on boiling with alcohol, water or dilute alkali. It dyes silk a yellow shade. (Found: C, 68.77; H, 3.91 $C_{10}H_6O_3$ requires C, 68.98; H, 3.45 per cent).

Condensation of β -resorcyaldehyde with pyruvic acid.—A mixture of pyruvic acid (3.5 c. c.), β -resorcyaldehyde (5 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c. c.), was heated at 200-20° for nearly 2 hours when a red compound separated. It was purified from acetic acid or alcohol. It dyes silk a red shade. (Found: C, 62.71; H, 3.90. $C_{10}H_7O_4$ requires C, 62.84; H, 3.67 per cent).

Condensation of glucose with pyruvic acid.—Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed for nearly 2 hours through a solution of glucose (8 g.) and pyruvic acid (4 c. c.) in alcohol (20 c. c.) and the whole thing was kept for 5 days. On pouring the mixture into water a deep red compound was obtained. It was purified by precipitation from dilute alcohol. It does not melt up to 240°. (Found: C, 46.34; H, 5.42. $C_9H_{12}O_7$ requires C, 46.34; H, 5.17 per cent).